

WEB ARCHIVING COLLECTIONS AS DATA

Ben O'Brien

National Library of New Zealand
New Zealand
ben.o'brien@dia.govt.nz
[https://orcid.org/
0000-0002-4290-2972](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4290-2972)

Gustavo Candela

University of Alicante
Spain
gcandela@ua.es
[https://orcid.org/
0000-0001-6122-0777](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6122-0777)

Helena Byrne

British Library
United Kingdom
helena.byrne@bl.uk
[https://orcid.org/
0000-0002-0966-4685](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0966-4685)

Jon Tønnessen

National Library of Norway
Norway
jon.tonnessen@nb.no
[https://orcid.org/
0000-0001-8861-0994](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8861-0994)

Olga Holownia

International Internet
Preservation Consortium
United States
olga@netpreserve.org
[https://orcid.org/
0000-0003-1800-6526](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1800-6526)

Yizhe Zhan

National Library of New
Zealand
New Zealand
yizhe.zahn@dia.govt.nz
[https://orcid.org/
0000-0003-2756-014X](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2756-014X)

Abstract – Cultural heritage institutions tasked with collecting and preserving born-digital content are continually exploring ways to make these resources accessible to users. This workshop presents the outcomes of a project focused on adapting a checklist for publishing digital collections to content derived from web archives. We will consider the unique challenges involved in providing access to web archive collections and suggest modifications needed to improve their documentation and accessibility. The workshop draws on several use cases and incorporates insights gathered from previous events on the topic aimed at web archiving professionals and researchers.

Submission Type – Workshop.

Keywords – Access, Born Digital Content, Web Archives Content, Workflows, Computational Access.

Conference Topics – Tūtaki (Encounter).

Community (<https://glamlabs.io/>) has explored innovative ways to publish and reuse the content provided by cultural heritage institutions. As part of their work, and as a collaborative effort, a checklist [2] was defined for publishing collections as data. It provides a set of steps that can be used for creating and evaluating digital collections suitable for computational use, but it has primarily been tested for digitized collections. While web archiving institutions and initiatives have been providing access to their collections, ranging from sharing seedlists to derivatives, to “cleaned” WARC files, there is currently no standardised checklist to prepare those collections for researchers. Our goal is to determine the feasibility of having a standardised method for making web archive collections available as data based on current practices at web archiving institutions and the GLAM Labs checklist.

I. COLLECTIONS AS DATA AND THE GLAM LABS CHECKLIST

GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums) have started to make available their digital collections suitable for computational use following the Collections as Data principles [1]. Importantly, the first principle mentions “responsible computation use” of both digitized and born-digital collections [1]. The International GLAM Labs

II. WEB ARCHIVES COLLECTIONS AS DATA

Web Archives Collections as Data (WACAD) is a project that builds on the experience of applying the checklist to digitized and born-digital collections, and on discussions, surveys, and feedback received during workshops delivered at the 2025 Digital

Humanities of the Nordic and Baltic Countries Conference [3] and the 2025 Web Archiving Conference [4]. In these cases, our goal was to involve web archiving practitioners as well as researchers in reevaluating whether the checklist could be adapted for web archive collections.

Our starting point was to compare the key differences between the checklist being applied to digitized and web archive collections at libraries that are members of the International Internet Preservation Consortium (IIPC) and also host Labs: the British Library, KB - the National Library of the Netherlands, Library of Congress, the National Library of Norway and the Royal Danish Library. We expanded this group to include more institutions during the workshops. The participants' feedback helped us identify the main challenges to applying the GLAM Labs checklist and determining which steps require refinements so that it can be used for web archive collections. We concluded that due to the complexity of web archive collections, such as issues related to licensing and privacy, and the multi-step workflow required to prepare the data for reuse, an annotated guide was needed to accompany the checklist rather than trying to modify it.

At this workshop, we will look at how the participating institutions have used the checklist and the guide to improve documentation and accessibility of their web archive collections. We will also test it on datasets provided by the National Library of New Zealand.

III. WORKSHOP STRUCTURE

In the first part of the workshop, we will introduce the key concepts, cover steps involved in publishing a web archive dataset while providing use cases from the British Library [5], the National Library of Norway [6], and the National Library of New Zealand.

The second part will involve testing the New Zealand Web Archive collections. The web archive consists of thematic, selective crawls and annual .nz domain crawls. The Library will provide a range of datasets that include longitudinal government data, covering aspects of the Te Reo Māori language, New Zealand's diverse culture and communities, and the delivery of public services. These datasets should aim to test the boundaries and the practicality of the checklist and the annotated guide.

IV. WORKSHOP OUTCOMES

The workshop aims to provide the following outcomes for attendees:

- Learn about the steps involved in preparing digitized and born-digital collections as published datasets.
- Understand the challenges involved in preparing web archive datasets and/or sharing with researchers and other users.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Padilla, H. Scates Kettler, S. Varner, and Y. Shorish, "Vancouver Statement on Collections as Data", *Collections as Data*, 2023, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8342171
- [2] G. Candela, et al., "A checklist to publish collections as data in GLAM institutions", *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*, 2023, doi: 10.1108/GKMC-06-2023-0195
- [3] O. Holownia, et al., "Web Archives Collections as Data", *Digital Humanities of the Nordic and Baltic Countries Conference*, 2025, Tartu, March 4.
- [4] O. Holownia, et al., "Web Archives Collections as Data" *IIPC Web Archiving Conference*, 2025, Oslo, April 9.
- [5] E. Maemura, and H. Byrne, "Datashets for Web Archives Toolkit", *British Library Research Repository*, 2024, doi: 10.22020/rq8z-r112
- [6] J.C. Tønnessen, and M.B. Birkenes, 'Providing Web Archive News Articles as Corpus Data', *Journal of Open Humanities Data*, 2025, 11(1), p. 2, doi: 10.5334/johd.281

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Ben O'Brien, Digital Preservation Web Engineer, NLNZ.

Gustavo Candela, Lecturer in Computer Science, University of Alicante.

Helena Byrne, Curator of Web Archives, BL.

Jon Carlstedt Tønnessen, Research Librarian, NLN.

Olga Holownia, IIPC Senior Program Officer.

Yizhe Zhan, Data Specialist, NLNZ.

